

BABOTS

Horizon Europe 101098722

*BABOTS:
The design and control of small swarming
biological animal robots*

Website and Project Logo

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1 Introduction

This deliverable describes the BABOTS project website and illustrates the BABOTS project logo. The project website includes the links to the social media (Facebook, LinkedIn and X, formerly Twitter) with the objective of implementing a multi-channel communication approach with the public. Moreover, we have implemented a private section on the website that allows to share private documents among the project members, to keep track of the project schedule through an interactive Gantt chart, and to manage the database of the website. This deliverable is structured as follows: in Section 2, we describe the current website, with its main features; in Sections 2.1 and 2.2, we describe the front-end and the back-end of the website, respectively; in Section 2.3, we describe the deployment method of the website. In Section 3, we show the project logo. Finally, in Section 4, we provide a brief conclusion.

2 Website

The project website can be found at www.babots.eu. It was first launched in November 2022 as a static web-page, including the logo and some general description of the project mainly written for a non-expert audience. With the beginning of the project in October 2023, the website has been redesigned entirely through a REST API approach and relaunched in November 2023 by the doctoral students Nemanja Antonic and Aymeric Vellinger at UNamur. The REST API links the front-end, implemented with the Angular Framework¹, to the back-end, implemented with the Django Rest Framework². These two frameworks have been chosen as they allow very quick and secure development through a modular approach, they are very well-recognized in the web development community and they allow for easy maintenance.

The homepage of the website shows an overview of the project, with a brief description of the project's objectives, the list of the Institutes that compose the project consortium, and the names and contact details of the principal investigators and of the researchers in each Institute (see Figures 1,2). Moreover, the homepage has a window that shows the project related news appeared on social media, and any relevant late-breaking news about the project activity. The news posted on social media and automatically displayed on the home page of the web site are limited to those from Facebook. We do not display news posted on X (former Twitter), because X, contrary to Twitter, offers this service only under rather expensive registration fees. The home page also displays the Google analytics. Note that, this service will be fully operative after two months from the deployment of the site. From the homepage, through a menu bar placed on the top side, the user can navigate the following sections:

- a **Project** section, which describes work packages WP1 to WP5, together with an illustration and the current status of the research progress in each WP (see Figure 3);
- a **Press** section, with a drop-down menu that lists, for each of the countries of the project partners, the project related press released appeared since October 2022 (see Figure 4);

¹<https://angular.io/>

²<https://www.django-rest-framework.org/>

Website and Project Logo (1.0)

BABOTS

Home | Project | Press | Publications | FAQ

BABOTS: THE DESIGN AND CONTROL OF SMALL SWARMING BIOLOGICAL ANIMAL ROBOTS

Funded by the Horizon Europe
EIC PathFinder European Innovation Council Work Programme
HORIZON-EIC-2022-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01
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A MULTIDISCIPLINARY PROJECT

We are the BABot consortium, funded by the European Innovation Council (EIC), and consisting of an international team of experts in neurobiology, synthetic biology, collective behaviour, robotics, and ethics, as well as a state-of-the-art agrotech company. Our goal is to develop and promote BABot technology, and demonstrate its utility and safety under a stringent ethical and regulatory framework.

We will implement the first BABot system in *C. elegans*, a 1 mm long nematode worm. Worm BABots will be programmed to act as a collective that will detect, locate and attack invading pathogens in a contained agricultural setting.

TEAM

University of Namur
Project Coordinator
Faculty of Computer Science
Belgium

The Hebrew University of Jerusalem
Israel

Institute of Cognitive Science and Technology
Italy

Max Planck Institute
Animal Behavior
Germany

Max Planck Institute
Neurobiology of Behavior
Germany

Aalto University
Finland

ZERO
Italy

NEWS

Babots
1 October

Babots
about a week ago

We are thrilled to announce that our project has fully started as we have held our kick-off meeting on the 20th of October with all the involved institutions of **Université de Namur Aalto University Max Planck Society The Hebrew University of Jerusalem ISTC CNR Babots italkit!**

Like Comment Share

BABOTS

BABOTS: des nouveaux robots biologiques belges?

European Innovation Council

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EIC PathFinder European Innovation Council Work Programme
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Grant No. 101098722

Contact:
babots@namur.be

Figure 1: Home page of the website.

Figure 2: Member section of the home page of the website after clicking on an Institute, in this case UNamur.

Figure 3: Project page of the website after selecting one workpackage, in this case WP1.

The screenshot shows the 'Press / Belgium' section of the BABOTS website. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the BABOTS logo on the left and links for Home, Project, Press, Publications, and FAQ on the right. Below the navigation bar, the page title 'Press / Belgium' is centered. The main content area features three article cards. The first card, titled 'L'UNamur va travailler sur des vers transgénétiques pour adapter leur système nerveux au service de l'agriculture, notamment', includes a sub-header 'Sudinfo', two images (one showing a green and white logo, the other a woman looking through a microscope), a short text snippet, the date 'Wed Nov 01 2023', and a 'See article' link. The second card, titled 'L'UNamur à la base d'un projet de recherche européen en bio-robotique', has a sub-header 'MediQuality', an image of several small white robots with the BABOTS logo and 'European Innovation' text, a text snippet, the date 'Sun Oct 01 2023', and a 'See article' link. The third card, titled 'BABOTS: des nouveaux robots biologiques belges?', has a sub-header 'RTBF', an image of the same robots with the BABOTS logo and 'European Innovation' text, a text snippet, the date 'Fri Jan 13 2023', and a 'See article' link. The fourth card, titled 'Université de Namur : des vers "programmés" pour travailler comme des robots', has a sub-header 'RTBF', an image of a glowing blue worm-like robot, a text snippet, the date 'Mon Jan 16 2023', and a 'See article' link.

Figure 4: Press page of the website after selecting one country, in this case Belgium.

The screenshot shows the FAQ page of the BABOTS website. The header is blue and contains the BABOTS logo on the left and navigation links (Home, Project, Press, Publications, FAQ) on the right. The main content area is white and features a list of 15 FAQ items. Each item consists of a question, a category label, and a dropdown arrow. The categories are: Generic, Ethical, and Technical. To the right of the list is a 'Filter by categories' section with three checkboxes: Generic, Ethical, and Technical, all of which are checked.

Question	Category
What are BABots?	Generic
Why are we developing BABots?	Generic
What will BABots be good for?	Generic
Will animals be hurt in this project?	Ethical
What are the environmental implications of BABots?	Ethical
What if BABots are released and get out of control?	Ethical
Will the BABot technology require new regulations?	Ethical
Does the BABot project have ethical implications?	Ethical
How are the neural circuits of C. elegans modified?	Technical
How do BABots differ from conventional robots?	Technical
How do BABots differ from genetically modified animals?	Technical
How do BABots differ from Biorobots and Xenobots?	Technical
Are BABots a form of synthetic biology?	Technical
"C. elegans sometimes behave like a collective, so why must this be engineered?"	Technical
What is vertical farming?	Technical
How is public engagement implemented in the BABot project?	Generic

Figure 5: FAQ page of the website.

- a **Publications** section, which lists all the publications. These publications are imported from the the project OpenAIRE, where all publications are made available to the public. Currently, this page is empty, as no publications are available yet;
- a **FAQ** section, which provides an informative description of the project objectives and research work in a language accessible to non-expert audience, with a easily readable question and answer format (see Figure 5).

Users given an authorization will be able to login (authenticate themselves) through a hidden login page. An authenticated user is able to access:

- a **Gantt chart** section, where a Gantt chart indicates the project organisation by listing the work packages, the deliverables and the milestones with the due-to-date and respective content. The Gantt also clearly marks the past from future activity;
- a **Manage press** section, where different types of items (e.g., press release, videos, etc.) related to the project dissemination activity can be added/removed from the database, and eventually shown on the **Press** section;
- a **Manage member** section, where the members of the project can be added or deleted;
- a **Manage project** section, where the project description of each WP can be updated;
- an **Add private document** section, where documents that are not marked as public, can be uploaded;
- a **Logout** button, which allows an authenticated user to logout.

Finally, the developers can use super-user credentials in order to access and edit the database of the website.

2.1 Front-end

The front-end of this application is a dynamic and responsive user interface that has been developed using the Angular framework. Angular is a popular and robust JavaScript framework that provides a structured and efficient way to build web applications.

The front-end follows a Model-View-Service (MVS) architecture, a variation of the more commonly known Model-View-Controller (MVC) pattern. In this architecture, the Model represents the data and business logic, the View is responsible for displaying the user interface, and the Service layer handles communication with the server and various application services.

One notable feature of the front-end is the implementation of a token interceptor. This interceptor automatically injects authentication tokens into outgoing requests when a user is connected, thereby providing seamless access to the member area of the application. This security feature enhances user experience and ensures that authorized users can access restricted content without the need to manually handle authentication tokens with each request.

In terms of programming languages and styling, the front-end uses TypeScript for scripting and SCSS (Sass) for styling. TypeScript is a statically typed superset of JavaScript, which helps catch

errors during development and provides better tooling for code navigation and refactoring. SCSS (Sass) is a preprocessor for CSS, offering features like variables, nesting, and mixins, which make styling the application more efficient and maintainable.

These language and styling choices combined with the architecture choice contribute to the overall robustness and maintainability of the front-end codebase.

Also, dynamic error handling for forms has been developed. This advanced error-handling mechanism ensures a seamless user experience by providing real-time feedback and guidance when users interact with forms.

In summary, the front-end of this application is built with Angular, follows a Model-View-Service architecture, employs a token interceptor for seamless authentication, and utilizes TypeScript and SCSS for code and styling, respectively. These technologies and architectural choices have been combined to create a well-structured and secure user interface for the application. A detailed version of the front-end implementation is shown in Figure 6.

2.2 Back-end

The back-end leverages the Django Rest Framework. It is built with models, each representing a table in a SQLite database. Each model has a number of attributes, each representing a row in that particular table. The contents of each attribute may be characters, numbers, dates, images, files or relationships to other models, such as one-to-one, one-to-many and many-to-many relationships. These models are then serialised through a set of serializers, one per model, that allows to transform the contents of the table (or of a single row) into a response which can be sent through an HTTP request. For models that have an image or a file field, a different type of response is required in order to serve them to the front-end, thus a serializer is built for each image and file entry. The serializers lay in views, where each view is treated as a class implementing GET and/or POST methods, which process a request and based on that they send a response, potentially operating directly on the database. Views, or their POST methods, may be subject to an authentication scheme, which requires the presence of a token in the authentication section of the header of the HTTP request. Tokens are generated through the Django Rest Knox package, which allows to have a single token for each user with an expiration date. In particular, the tokens are generated through a SHA512 hashing algorithm and refresh every 10 hours. Finally, the views are made available through URLs accessible via the API. A detailed version of the back-end implementation is shown in Figure 7.

2.3 Deployment method

We deploy the website leveraging Docker compose³. In particular, we create and compose two containers: one for the front-end and one for the back-end. These containers are created with a Dockerfile, which creates a container based on an image. The back-end Dockerfile leverages the latest Python image, allowing to install the required packages in the container and starting the back-end server. The front-end Dockerfile, on the other hand, leverages the latest official Node image as the foundation, in which we set up the working directory, copy the source code,

³<https://docs.docker.com/compose/>

and install dependencies. We then serve the application with an Nginx server on the port 80.

The Docker compose instance is hosted on a proxy server managed by UNamur, which can be accessed through a VPN for deployment and maintenance.

3 Logo

The project's logo has been designed by Dr Monika Scholz, one of the principal investigator at the project partner Max-Planck-Gesellschaft (MPG). The logo combines the following four elements: i) the project acronym, ii) the drawing of the worms *C. elegans*, iii) the stars inspired by those on the Europe Union flag, and iv) the O forming the shape of a plasmid, indicating the bio-engineering aspect of the babots. In Figure 9, we show the logo in its three different format: the horizontal one (see Figure 9a), the square one (see Figure 9b), and the vertical one (see Figure 9c).

4 Conclusions

We have developed the official website for the BABOTS project and successfully implemented the multi-channel approach, activating all the social media. We have designed the logo of the project to be used in all these scenarios. We plan to use the website both to keep in touch with the public and to maximize the efficiency of our internal communication, providing an easy-to-use tool that allows the members of the project to keep track of news, publications, private documents and of the project status. Finally, we allow an easy maintenance of the website through a developer login.

Figure 6: Angular framework front-end: with components (in red), models (in green), handlers (in blue) and services (in yellow).

Figure 7: Django Rest Framework back-end: with paths (in yellow), views (in red), serializers (in green), imported serializer from a package (in purple), and models (in blue)

Figure 8: Detailed structure of the network architecture

Figure 9: The BABOTS project's logo in its three different format: (a) the horizontal logo, (b) the square logo, and (c) the vertical logo.